

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH OF THE ELECTROMECHANICAL PART OF A THREE-PHASE ELECTROMAGNETIC EXCITER OF LOW-FREQUENCY MECHANICAL VIBRATIONS

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Abstract

The article examines a number of features of energy processes in the “three-phase traction electromagnet-capacitor” system with continuous oscillatory motion of the armature electromagnet. It is assumed that the amplitude of mechanical vibrations can be quite large. According to this judgment, regarding the possibility of obtaining low-frequency mechanical oscillations in the range (0÷20) Hz using a three-phase electromagnetic traction system, it should be considered appropriate to consider in detail the processes in the specified device when it is connected according to circuits with series capacitors in a standard network. Such consideration would make it possible to clarify the design conditions of these devices, which helps to improve their design.

Keywords: three-phase power system, electromagnetic exciter, low-frequency mechanical vibrations, spectral composition, magnetic flux.

Introduction. As is known, one of the widespread vibration exciters of low-frequency mechanical vibrations in the subsonic frequency range is a single-phase electromagnetic exciter [1-4], the winding of which is connected through a series capacitor to a standard power supply network. This single-phase version of the exciter is discussed with the necessary completeness in the indicated literary sources. However, the development of its three-phase analogue requires further study of the processes in this type of device. Due to the fact that the basis for the functioning of the pathogen under consideration is, as already mentioned, the choice of the rational formation of the component of traction force alternating in sign at the frequency of mechanical oscillations, an assessment of these conditions is used for further research [5,6].

The traction force of an electromagnetic exciter of low-frequency mechanical vibrations, as in any traction electromagnet, is associated with the magnitude of the magnetic flux components in the magnetic system of these exciters. Therefore, studying the components of magnetic flux contributes to the success of subsequent research. Since the results of such studies are known for single-phase electromagnetic exciters, it is advisable to turn to such schemes of three-phase exciters of low-frequency mechanical oscillations that would allow a fairly simple comparison of the processes in them with

similar ones in single-phase exciters [7-10]. The possibility of obtaining low-frequency mechanical oscillations in the range (0÷20) Hz using a three-phase electromagnetic traction system makes it relevant to take a detailed look at the processes in the specified device when it is connected to an electrical network using circuits with series capacitors. Such consideration would make it possible to clarify the design conditions of a three-phase electromagnetic vibration exciter of low-frequency mechanical vibrations (TEMV LFMV), which helps to increase efficiency and improve their design.

Selecting a rational scheme for switching on the TEMV LFMV and justifying the possibility of symmetrical loading in its mechanical part

The circuit for a three-phase electromagnetic vibration exciter is shown in Picture 1 [11]. It is assumed that the vibration exciter has identical windings on all three rods of the W-shaped magnetic circuit, which are connected in a star and connected to a three-phase standard power supply network through three identical capacitors connected in series. The armature, making oscillatory movements, moves back and forth and changes the size of the air gap in phase for all three rods. In this case, the three-phase exciter provides a

symmetrical load of the phases of the three-phase circuit, and for subsequent studies, processes in each phase (in each winding) can be considered in isolation.

Let us consider in more detail the symmetry condition in the diagram in Picture 1.

Picture 1. Design diagram of three-phase electromagnetic exciter of low-frequency mechanical vibrations (TEMV LFMV)

The main sign of the symmetry of the load of the phases of a three-phase circuit when connecting the source and consumer according to the star-star circuit without a neutral wire is the condition of the absence of neutral bias voltage: $U_{00} = 0$

In this case, the sum of phase currents:

$$i_A + i_B + i_C = 0. \quad (1)$$

Turning to identifying the reasons for the presence of such conditions (in particular (1 a)), in our case we note the following. As is known:

$$V_{00} = \frac{E_A Y_A + E_B Y_B + E_C Y_C}{Y_A + Y_B + Y_C}, \quad (2)$$

$\dot{E}_A, \dot{E}_B, \dot{E}_C$ – complex values of phase EMFs. conditional three-phase power supply when connected to a star; Y_A, Y_B, Y_C – complex values of the phase admittances of a consumer connected in a star.

In our case, the total conductivity of the n - phase is

$$Y_n = g_n + jb_n, \quad (3)$$

Where g_n, b_n – respectively, the active and reactive components of the admittance. Because the

$$b_n = b_{Ln} - b_{Cn},$$

Where b_L, b_C – respectively, the inductive and capacitive components of reactive conductivity, then the inductive resistance of the phase windings of the considered three-phase electromagnetic exciter of low-frequency mechanical vibrations $X_{Ln} = \omega L_n$ - (where ω – angular frequency of supply, L_n – inductance n – windings are associated with conductivity values b_{Ln} - impedance n – phase of the user.

$$Z_n = \sqrt{r_n^2 + (X_{Ln} - X_{Cn})^2},$$

Where r_n – active resistance n – thought phase

$X_{Cn} = \frac{1}{\omega C_n}$ - capacitive resistance, C_n – capacity

n – to the condenser. We will also note that

$$g_n = \frac{r_n}{z_n^2}; b_{Ln} = \frac{X_{Ln}}{z_n^2}; b_{Cn} = \frac{X_{Cn}}{z_n^2}; \quad (4)$$

Thus, the numerical values of all conductivity g_n, b_{Ln} and b_{Cn} through Z_n according to (2-4) are related to the value of the inductive resistance X_{Ln} , defined by inductance L_n , n - winding of the considered three-phase exciter.

But the magnitude of the inductance itself L_n is connected with the geometrical characteristics of the magnetic wire of the oscillation exciter, in particular, with the size of the air gap δ . As you know, the inductance of the windings located on the core (in particular, on the p-core) is determined as:

$$L_n = \frac{w_n \Phi_n}{I_n} = \frac{w^2 M_0}{\delta + \delta_\phi}, \quad (5)$$

Where w_n – number of turns of the n -th winding;

Φ_n – magnetic flux coupled to the n -th winding;

I_n – current in turns of the n -th winding; δ_ϕ – a certain amount of air gap (fictitious air gap), the introduction of which makes it possible to take into account the fundamental presence of magnetic resistance of steel.

Based on this, in the absence of magnetic saturation in steel, the value δ_ϕ significantly small compared

to the actual air gap δ_ϕ in the magnetic system of the considered TEMV LFMV in $\delta_\phi \ll \delta$. In this regard, in (5) it can be omitted as an explicit component, but its presence is taken into account as follows. In picture. Picture 2 shows a section of the magnetic circuit of the exciter in question, containing n -th rod with winding, air gap and movable armature. It is assumed that the armature performs its oscillatory movements, having a certain average air gap δ_0 , relative to which it shifts in time by $x(t)$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(t) + x(t) &= \delta_0 \\ \delta(t) &= \delta_0 - x(t). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

At the same time, taking into account the fundamental presence δ_0 , there are strict inequalities:

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &< \delta_0 \\ \delta(t) &> 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Note that the direction $x(t)$ is chosen to be positive in the case of attraction of the movable armature to the yoke, that is, according to the conditionally positive direction of the traction force F_p on the rod with the winding. This subsequently facilitates the physical interpretation of a number of analytical results. Thus, (5) taking into account (6) and (7) has the form

$$L_n(t) = \frac{M^2 M_0 S_M}{\delta(t)} = \frac{K}{\delta(t)}, \quad (8)$$

Where $K^2 = w^2 M_0 S_M$ - does not depend on time (based on the explanations to (5)).

Turning to (3), (4) and the explanations, we note that Y_n depends on $\delta(t)$.

Picture 2. Section of the magnetic circuit TEMV LFMV

However, at the beginning of this paragraph it was indicated that a three-phase electromagnetic exciter is being considered, the armature of which “changes the size of the air gap of all three rods” [12]. If the geometry of the rods, the number of turns of the windings on them, the capacitances of the capacitors and the structural elements of the armature are the same, the coefficient K_b (8) and the law of variation of the gap are the same for all three rods. Then:

$$L_A(t) = L_B(t) = L_C(t) = L_N(t) \quad (9)$$

and therefore

$$Y_A(t) = Y_B(t) = Y_C(t) = Y_N(t). \quad (10)$$

In this case (2) will take the form

$$U_{00} = \frac{(E_A + E_B + E_C) \cdot Y_N}{3Y_N} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$E_A + E_B + E_C = 0$$

The above considerations allow us to see that in the circuit of Picture 1, condition (1 a) is satisfied and, therefore, each of the three phases can be considered conditionally in isolation, taking into account the fact that:

$$E_n - V_{00} = V_{\phi_n}.$$

Since according to (10) $U_{00} = 0$, then (11) will take the form

$$E_n = V_{\phi_n} \quad (12)$$

and consideration of a three-phase design comes down to comparison with a single-phase version of an electromagnetic exciter of low-frequency mechanical oscillations with a series capacitor. Note that condition (6) is satisfied only for the circuit in Picture 1. If the windings of a three-phase exciter are connected in a triangle, it may be damaged. This issue will be addressed in subsequent chapters.

Spectral composition of magnetic fluxes and currents in the rods and phases of a three-phase electromagnetic exciter

Research carried out according to the scheme in Picture . 1 yielded some results that, when compared with the results of other works, force us to introduce additional adjustments in the interpretation of the ongoing processes. This concerns, first of all, the harmonic composition of the magnetic flux for the n-th (any) TEMV LFMV rod. Let's consider what has been said in more detail. We will consider the formation of an alternating component in the traction force of each of the rods of a three-phase structure at the frequency of mechanical vibrations of the armature to be similar to the same process in a single-phase electromagnetic exciter of mechanical vibrations. Then we will apply the approach of identifying the harmonic components of the current. in the winding, formed in, to establish the necessary harmonic composition of currents in each of the windings of a three-phase design. The essence of the method is that a connection is sought between the harmonic compositions of the current $i(t)$ and the magnetic flux $\Phi(t)$, based on (5) and (8) for a given change in the air gap $\delta(t)$ by the moving armature and any of the three-rod cores designs, that is:

$$I(t) = k\Phi(t)\delta(t), \quad (13)$$

$$I(t) = I_{\Sigma}(t) = k \left[\dots + \Phi_{k-1} \sin(\omega_{(k-1)}t + a_{k-1}) + \Phi_k \sin(\omega_k(t) + a_k) + \Phi_{k+1} \sin(\omega_{(k+1)}t + a_{k+1}) \right] \quad (18)$$

In an expression like (16), only two components are considered at a minimum (at frequencies $\omega_{(k)}N\omega_{(k+1)}$). At the same time, their sufficiency was noted. However, studies conducted in three-phase pathogens did not confirm this position. Let us consider the emerging objections in more detail. "Considering that a process characterized by a harmonic composition with a minimum number of components is stationary in the case of an oscillatory system, we will consider it" [13]. At the same time, we note that the harmonic components of the magnetic flux determine the presence of the

$$I_A(t) = I_{\Sigma}(t) = k\Phi_m\delta_0 \left[\sum_{g=1}^{\infty} J_k \sin(\omega_{(k)}t + ak) + [1 - \beta \sin(\nu t + \Theta)] \right] \quad (21)$$

Where Φ_m - is a certain normalizing value of the amplitude of the magnetic flux of a given phase of a three-phase exciter;

$$J_k = \frac{\phi_k}{\phi_m} - \text{amplitude coefficient of the } k\text{-th harmonic component of the magnetic flux;}$$

monic component of the magnetic flux;

$$\beta = \frac{X_m}{\delta_0} - \text{displacement harmonic amplitude coefficient.}$$

Based on this, after transformation into (21) we obtain:

$$I_A(t) = I_{\Sigma}(t) = I_0 \left[\sum_1^{\infty} A_K \sin(\omega_{(k)}t + \zeta_k) \right], \quad (22)$$

Where $I_0 = K\Phi_m\delta_0$ - standard current value $I(t)$,

$$\text{Where } K = \frac{W}{K} = \frac{1}{WMSm} - \text{design factor.}$$

Considering that in the general case

$$\Phi(t) = \Phi_{\Sigma}(t) = \sum_{g=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \Phi_{jm}^{(g)} \sin(\omega_j t + aj) \quad (14)$$

Where the internal sum is the Fourier series whose fundamental frequencies are $-\omega_n$.

$$nT_k = mT_{k-1} = \dots = T$$

or

$$n \frac{2\pi}{\omega(t)} = m \frac{2\pi}{\omega(k-1)} = \dots = \frac{2\pi}{\omega} \quad (15)$$

we will apply to $\Phi(t)$ in (13) for subsequent reasoning $\Phi_{\Sigma}(t)$:

$$\Phi_{\Sigma}(t) = \sum_{g=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \Phi_{jm}^{(g)} \sin(\omega_j t + aj) \quad (16)$$

The number of components in (16) will be set below. Turning to the factor $\delta(t)$ in (13), we note that it is sufficient to restrict ourselves in (6) to the expression

$$x(t) = X_m \sin(\nu t + \Theta) \quad (17)$$

Practice shows that other harmonics of the Fourier type in (17) have an insignificant influence when studying the basic current components in (13) for a stationary process of operation of the oscillation exciter and can be omitted.

corresponding components of the inductive voltage $u_{L(k)m}$ on the winding. But it is known that

$$u_{L(k)m} = W\omega_{(k)}\Phi_{(k)}. \quad (19)$$

Thus,

$$u_L(t) = u_{L\Sigma}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} W\omega_k\Phi_{(k)m} \cos(\omega_k t + a_k) \quad (20)$$

It follows that in the presence of an experimentally obtained oscillogram of the process, where the voltage, $u_L(t)$ is recorded, the number of fundamental harmonics in expression (4) can be established.

Carrying out transformations in (18), we obtain:

A_K, ζ_k - respectively, the amplitude coefficient and phase of the harmonic component then $I_A(t)$.

In (22), the quantities included in it are defined as follows. Amplitude coefficient of the k -th harmonic component:

$$A_k = \sqrt{J_{(k)}^2 + \frac{\beta^2(J_{(k-1)} - J_{(k-1)})}{4}}. \quad (23)$$

The phase of the k -th harmonic component of the current ζ_k is determined from the following considerations:

$$\zeta_k = p_k + a_k. \quad (24)$$

Thus, form (22), taking into account (23) and (24), allows us to see the influence of harmonic components

(through coefficients J_k) on the formation of the corresponding harmonic current components (Picture. 3) and, therefore, establishes the correction of current components (belonging to the electrical subsystem) and magnetic flux components (belonging to the magnetic subsystem) [14-16].

$$p_k = \arctg \left[\frac{\beta(J_{(k-1)} - J_{(k+1)})}{2J_k} \right] \quad (25)$$

Turning to the formation of the alternating component of the traction force of the exciter of low-frequency mechanical vibrations, we note that (remove the

comma) the third harmonic component in the magnetic flux entails changes in the amplitude-frequency characteristics of the traction force. Let us turn to the consideration of the equations for the electrical subsystem of the TEMV LFMV. Due to the fact that both harmonic representations of magnetic fluxes (13) and harmonic representations of currents (22) in the exciter windings were formed above, it is advisable to present these equations with the introduction of the indicated quantities. Then for the diagram in Picture . 1 these equations will take the form

Picture 3.

Influence of harmonic components of magnetic flux on the formation of harmonic components of current

$$\begin{aligned} U_a &= I_a r_a + \frac{1}{C_a} \int I_a dt + W_a \frac{d}{dt} (\Phi_a) \\ U_b &= I_b r_b + \frac{1}{C_b} \int I_b dt + W_b \frac{d}{dt} (\Phi_b) \\ U_c &= I_c r_c + \frac{1}{C_c} \int I_c dt + W_c \frac{d}{dt} (\Phi_c), \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

U_{abc} – phase voltages according to phases A, B and C;

$r_a = r_b = r_c = r$ – active resistance of phase windings A, B and C;

Φ_a, Φ_b, Φ_c – magnetic fluxes in phase rods A, B and C;

$C_a = C_b = C_c = C$ – capacitance of capacitors in phases A, B and C;

$W_a = W_b = W_c = W$ – magnetic fluxes in phase rods A, B and C.

In this case, the equation of the mechanical part in accordance with (3) will take the form:

$$m \frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} + r_{mex} \frac{dx}{dt} + \frac{1}{\lambda} = F_{\Sigma} \quad (27)$$

Turning to (26), we note that the equations include both currents in the exciter windings and magnetic fluxes Φ . However, taking into account that, in accordance with (22), currents can be represented through components of magnetic fluxes, in equations (26) only

magnetic fluxes can be considered as variables. In addition, taking into account the above considerations about the symmetry of the load of the phases of a three-phase circuit, each of equations (2) can be considered in isolation, taking into account the fact that the magnetic fluxes must have the same harmonic composition, each of the components of which has the same amplitudes with operators of the “sin” type or “cos” of the same frequency, but different phase angles. The latter is related to the following considerations. The composition of magnetic fluxes must necessarily contain harmonic components (which, generally speaking, are dominant compared to other harmonic components), the frequency of which is determined by the frequency of the supply network. Due to the fact that the electromagnetic exciter under consideration is powered from a three-phase network, where shifts of phase voltages between each other at angles of 120° are determined, these phase shifts should also be contained in the arguments of the above-mentioned harmonic components of magnetic fluxes at the supply frequency, which we will further denote ω_k . At the same time, the phase shifts of the harmonic components of magnetic fluxes at frequencies do not have such an obvious indication for establishing the presence of the indicated angles in them, characteristic of a three-phase system.

However, special studies carried out made it possible to establish the presence of phase angles of 120° in the harmonic components of magnetic fluxes at frequencies different from the frequency ω_k . The main result of these studies is the following experimentally

confirmed consideration. Since modulation is carried out in windings located on all three rods of the magnetic wire with the help of a common armature (and, therefore, in phase, which is confirmed by oscillograms of the voltages on the indicated windings), then when the shape of the envelopes for these three voltages coincides, a shift of one of their harmonic components along phase at 120° entails the appearance of corresponding shifts in other harmonic components in order to maintain the constancy of the resulting shape of a given harmonic package. In passing, we note that the same considerations are valid for considering the phases in packets of harmonic current composition. The

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_{\Sigma A}(t) &= \Phi_{(k-1)} \sin(\omega_{(k-1)} + a_{k-1}) + \Phi_k \sin(\omega_{(k)} + a_k) + \Phi_{(k+1)} \sin(\omega_{(k+1)} + a_{k+1}) \\ \Phi_{\Sigma B}(t) &= \Phi_{(k-1)} \sin(\omega_{(k-1)} + a_{k-1} - 120) + \Phi_k \sin(\omega_{(k)} + a_k - 120) + \Phi_{(k+1)} \sin(\omega_{(k+1)} + a_{k+1} - 120) \\ \Phi_{\Sigma C}(t) &= \Phi_{(k-1)} \sin(\omega_{(k-1)} + a_{k-1} - 240) + \Phi_k \sin(\omega_{(k)} + a_k - 240) + \Phi_{(k+1)} \sin(\omega_{(k+1)} + a_{k+1} - 240)\end{aligned}\quad (28)$$

If we expand each term (28) in accordance with the well-known trigonometric formula $\sin(a+b)$, taking the phase shift in any of the phases equal to, we obtain taking into account that

$$a_k = \omega_k t + a_k \text{ и } b_k = \psi_k,$$

$$\Phi_{\Sigma n}(t) = \cos \Phi_{(n)} \sin(\Phi_{(k-1)} \sin a_{k-1}) + \Phi_k \sin a_k + \Phi_{(k+1)} \sin a_{k+1} + \dots$$

Turning to power phases A, B and C, we assume equal to ψ_n (0°) for phase (A), (-120°) for phase (B), (-240°) for phase (C). Taking into account the numerical values of the functions $\sin \psi$ $\cos \psi$ for $\psi=0^\circ$, (-120°), (-240°), we rewrite (29), noting that the factor of these functions is the sine and cosine components Φ_{Σ} at ψ_n (that is, for example, for phase A).

Then:

$$\psi_n = \psi_a = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_{\Sigma A}(t) &= \cos(0)(\Phi_{(k-1)} \sin a_{k-1} + \Phi_k \sin a_k + \Phi_{k+1} \sin a_{k+1}) + \\ &+ \sin(0)(\Phi_{(k-1)} \cos a_{k-1} + \Phi_{(k)} \cos a_k + \Phi_{(k+1)} \cos a_{k+1})\end{aligned}\quad (29)$$

For

$$\Phi_n = \Phi_B = 120$$

$$\Phi_{\Sigma B}(t) = \cos(120)\Phi_{\Sigma a \sin} + \sin(-120) + \Phi_{\Sigma A(\cos)}\quad (30)$$

The obtained relations (30) show that, while observing the symmetry of the parameters of the winding circuits of a three-phase electromagnetic exciter and its power supply system, there is symmetry in the distribution of not only the parameters of the harmonic components of magnetic fluxes at the supply frequency, but also the parameters of the harmonic components of magnetic fluxes at side frequencies:

$$\omega_{k-1} \text{ or } \omega_{k+1}\quad (31)$$

$$\Phi_{\Sigma a} + \Phi_{\Sigma B} + \Phi_{\Sigma C} = 0\quad (32)$$

Taking into account the presence in $\Phi_{\Sigma m}$ of harmonic components ω_{k-1} and ω_{k+1} . In passing, we

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{h} F_{\Sigma}(t) &= \frac{3}{2} \Phi_{k-1}^2 + \frac{3}{2} \Phi_k^2 + \frac{3}{2} \Phi_{k+1}^2 + 3\Phi_k \Phi_{k-1} \cos[(\omega_k + \omega_{k-1})t + (a_k + a_{k-1})] + \\ &+ 3\Phi_k + \Phi_k \cos[(\omega_{k+1} + \omega_k)t + (a_{k+1} + a_k)] + 3\Phi_{k+1} \Phi_k \cos[(\omega_{k+1} + \omega_k)t + (a_{k+1} + a_k)]\end{aligned}\quad (34)$$

appearance of phase shifts by (0°), (-120°), (-240°), determined by the influence of the three-phase power system, in all components of the harmonic composition of the corresponding magnetic fluxes requires additional and more detailed consideration of a number of circumstances related to the functioning of the TEMV LFMV. First of all, we note the following feature of the formation of conditional packages of magnetic fluxes of individual magnetic wire rods. Let us imagine the packages of magnetic fluxes in accordance with the connection of the windings that create them to the three-phase power supply in the form (16):

note that this result is consistent with the judgments discussed above in Picture 3, made on the basis of what is stated regarding the appearance of phase shifts in the lateral harmonic components of individual phases while maintaining the shape that envelops the packets of these harmonic components. However, in accordance with (27), the traction force of the TEMV NChK, taking into account the above, is determined by the summation of the values of magnetic fluxes, each of which is squared. Therefore:

$$F_{\Sigma} = F_{\Sigma}(t) = h[\Phi^2(t) + \Phi_{\Sigma B}^2(t)].\quad (33)$$

For convenience, we rewrite (32), normalizing by h .

First of all, we note that in connection with symmetry, that is, equalities, the summation of constant components (the first three terms in (33)) and harmonic components at difference frequencies is carried out. Note that, in accordance with Picture 3, the following frequency components are presented here:

$$\omega_{k+1} - \omega_k = \omega_k - \omega_{k-1} = \nu$$

$$F_{\Sigma}(t) \frac{3}{2} h(\Phi_{k-1}^2 + \Phi_k^2 + \Phi_{k+1}^2) + 3h\Phi_{k-1} \cos[(\omega_k + \Theta)t + (a_k + a_{k-1})] + 3h\Phi_{k+1} \Phi_k \cos[(\omega_{k+1} + \Theta)t + (a_{k+1} + a_k)] + 3h\Phi_{k+1} \Phi_k \cos[(\omega_{k+1} + \Theta)t + (a_{k+1} + a_k)] \quad (36)$$

or, using the elements of the notation form (21), (22) and (23), in particular we have:

$$F_{\Sigma}(t) \frac{3}{2} h(\Phi_m^2 (J_{k-1}^2 + J_k^2 + J_{k+1}^2) + 3h\Phi_m^2 J_{k-1} J_{k+1} \cos 2(\nu t + \Theta) + 3h\Phi_m^2 J_k (J_{k-1} J_{k+1}) \cos(\nu t + \Theta)) \quad (37)$$

Expression (37) can be presented in another form

$$F_{OTH}(t) = \frac{F_{\Sigma}(t)}{F_m} \left(\frac{1}{2} J_{k-1}^2 + \frac{1}{2} J_k^2 + \frac{1}{2} J_{k+1}^2 \right) + J_{k-1} J_{k+1} \cos 2(\nu t + \Theta) + J_k (J_{k-1} J_{k+1}) \cos(\nu t + \Theta) \quad (38)$$

Where $F_m = 3h\Phi_m^2$ – some normalizing value of the traction force of a three-phase electromagnetic exciter of low-frequency mechanical vibrations. Expressions (37) and (38) show that the harmonic composition of the traction force $F_{\Sigma}(t)$ acting on the TEMV LFMV armature (and through the latter on the working body of the technological object driven into reciprocating motion) is determined by two main groups of components. The first of them contains components that are independent of time and only attract the armature, as well as components that act on the armature with a frequency of 2ν (twice compared to the working frequency, equal to ν). All components of this group do not have a working effect on anchor, and in principle should be minimized. The second group is represented by two components that can be combined (which is done in (38)). Their combined force, which is an alternating disturbing force on ν , provides the necessary (working) movement of the anchor, and hence the working body. In principle, this force component in its amplitude exceeds the amplitude of the force component that disturbs the armature with double the frequency. Picture 5 shows the spectrum corresponding to (38) with the ratio of the magnetic flux amplitudes in Picture 3 c. Here it is easy to see the dominant position of the group of components traction force having a frequency ν . Note that the side frequencies $\omega=0$ and $\omega=2$ are spaced from the center line of the spectrum by an equal frequency interval. Thus, already at this stage of considering the processes in the TEMV LFMV, one can note a significant advantage regarding the formation of electromagnetic traction force in it. It should be provided for in minimizing the amplitudes of forces at side frequencies and isolating the main alternating component of the force at the operating frequency, both through the rational choice of the counter parameters r ,

$$a_{k+1} - a_k = a_k - a_{k-1} = \Theta$$

It follows that

$$\omega_{k+1} - \omega_{k-1} = 2\nu$$

$$a_{k+1} - a = 2\Theta \quad (35)$$

Thus, (35) must also be rewritten, and taking into account these expressions it will take the form:

L, C of each phase, and through three-phase power supply with a symmetrical load of a three-phase supply network of standard frequency. It is the latter that makes it possible to cancel a significant group of traction force components due to the presence of phase angles (0°), (-120°), (-240°) in them and to concentrate the transmitted power in a limited number of working components of this force. All this significantly contributes to increasing efficiency of the considered TEMV LFMV.

Results of modeling the operation of TEMV LFMV

An oscillogram of the operating parameters of the TEMV LFMV is shown in Picture 4. It shows the processes of changing $\delta(t), I_a(t), u_{LA}(t), u_{LB}(t), u_{LC}(t)$ that is, respectively, changes in the gap, current in phase A, voltage on the coils in phases A, B and C over time, the periodicity of which over the longest period (envelope period) is determined by stationarity mode of armature oscillations (changes in the air gap in $\delta(t)$). Analyzing with the help of the indicated oscillogram the nature of the change in voltages $u_{LA}(t), u_{LB}(t), u_{LC}(t)$, we note a “pronounced modulation of the processes” [17]. In this case, the symmetry of the envelopes relative to the abscissa axes (ωt -axes) can be traced for all three processes. However, the asymmetry of these envelopes relative to the conventional ordinate axis drawn from the center of each packet of oscillations (rectangle on the oscillogram in Picture 4) is just as clearly presented, which distinguishes the nature of this type of modulated curve from the nature of the beats, which in the classical form are formed by only two oscillations of a sinusoidal shape with identical amplitudes and similar frequencies. The latter, as is known, are characterized by a form in which there is symmetry of the envelopes both relative to the abscissa axis and the ordinate axis

in the above sense. The latter indicates that in the case of the law of change $u_L(t)$ (Picture. 4), when decomposing them into harmonic components, more than two similar components with different frequencies must be taken into account. The analysis showed that at least three harmonic components should be identified when decomposing $u_L(t)$. Confirmation of the validity is that in this case the cyclic graph Φ (b) is valid (Picture. 5, a), which is constructed in connection with the recommendations.

It was found that in such cases the frequencies of the three harmonics should be related to each other as (15). In this case, the period, which is the smallest common multiple of the periods of these harmonics, is the

period of mechanical oscillations of the armature, that is, $\delta(t)$. The amplitudes of the harmonic components of the magnetic flux are distributed in accordance with Picture 5, b. From Picture . 5b it is clear that the amplitude of harmonics with a conventionally average frequency should be greater than the amplitude of harmonics with side frequencies. The frequency of this “average” harmonic coincides with the frequency of the mains supply. The curve is formed by the summation of three harmonic components at various combinations of their amplitudes, the frequencies of which are subject to the above condition. It illustrates the correctness of these judgments regarding the shape of the modulated curve envelope with a similar harmonic composition.

Picture. 4.

Regularities of changes in the gap, current in phase A, voltage on the coils in phases A, B and C over time

Picture 5. Patterns of changes in operating parameters of TEMV LFMV
 a - cyclic graph $\Phi(\delta)$; b - amplitudes of the harmonic components of the magnetic flux

However, when discussing individual issues of filtration in the exciter phases, it is necessary to provide a theoretical justification for the appearance in the harmonic composition of the magnetic flux of precisely three harmonic components that satisfy the above considerations in terms of amplitudes and frequencies. In this case, the frequency values coincide with conditions (37) as in Picture 5. The considered harmonic components of the magnetic flux make it possible to determine the magnitude and harmonic composition of the electromagnetic force of the TEMV NChK, which, in principle, already allows for the possibility of its design. However, a feature of the considered type of exciter of low-frequency mechanical oscillations is a significant difference in the frequency of its supply from the frequency of mechanical oscillations, and frequency conversions occur inside the exciter device and are associated with modulation (parametric) effects. To more fully take into account their influence, it is advisable to turn to the electrical part of the three-phase exciter, dividing it into electrical, magnetic and mechanical subsystems. It is in its electrical subsystem that the restriction of conditions is formed, which determines the presence of a rational range of operating frequencies, which is associated with the fact of resonant filtering, which will be discussed below. For a detailed consideration of these issues, we will compose a convenient form of harmonic representation of currents in the windings of the exciter, and, using it, we will consider

the systems of equation of its electrical subsystem. The indicated form of representation of the harmonic components of the current can be obtained based on (18). In principle, this relationship should be obtained by integrating the equations for the electrical part of the exciter. However, the use of (18) makes it possible to establish a connection between the amplitudes, frequencies and phases of harmonics of currents and magnetic fluxes of a three-phase exciter, taking into account modulation effects in a form convenient for subsequent analysis, and therefore it is advisable to use this particular technique.

CONCLUSIONS

1. For the rational design of TEMV LFMV, it is necessary to consider in detail the conditions for the formation of currents in its windings and the features of the transfer of average power from the electrical subsystem to the mechanical one. As a result of studies of individual issues of filtration in the exciter phases, a theoretical justification is given for the appearance in the harmonic composition of the magnetic flux of three harmonic components that satisfy the amplitudes and frequencies. The considered harmonic components of the magnetic flux make it possible to determine the magnitude and harmonic composition of the electromagnetic force of the TEMV LFMV, which, in principle, already allows for the possibility of its design.

2. It has been determined that there is a significant difference between the power supply frequency of the TEMV LFMV and the frequency of its mechanical oscillations, and frequency conversions occur inside the exciter device and are associated with modulation (parametric) effects. To more fully take into account their influence, it is advisable to turn to the electrical part of the three-phase exciter, dividing it into electrical, magnetic and mechanical subsystems. It is in its electrical subsystem that the limitation of conditions is formed, which determines the presence of a rational range of operating frequencies, which is associated with the fact of resonant filtering.

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